

THE DAMAGE OF LOW-VELOCITY IMPACTED CFRP LAMINATES WITH DIFFERENT STACKING SEQUENCES BASED ON MICRO-MECHANICS OF FAILURE

Xiaofei Lou¹, Hongneng Cai², Xuecheng Han³, Fei Jiao⁴

¹ State Key Laboratory for Mechanical Behavior of Materials, Xi'an Jiaotong University,
Xi'an 710049, China, E-mail: feixiaolou@stu.xjtu.edu.cn

² State Key Laboratory for Mechanical Behavior of Materials, Xi'an Jiaotong University,
Xi'an 710049, China, E-mail: hntsai@mail.xjtu.edu.cn

³ State Key Laboratory for Mechanical Behavior of Materials, Xi'an Jiaotong University,
Xi'an 710049, China, E-mail: 1534152210@qq.com

⁴ State Key Laboratory for Mechanical Behavior of Materials, Xi'an Jiaotong University,
Xi'an 710049, China, E-mail: 875305569@qq.com

Keywords: Low-velocity impact, MMF, Cohesive, Stacking sequence;

ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminate has excellent properties of high stiffness and high strength. However, it is susceptible to external impact loading which would cause delaminations. In order to realize the safe design of composite structure, accurate prediction of strength of CFRP structure according to the failure mechanisms is vitally important. In this paper, a multiscale analysis method based on micro-mechanics of failure (MMF) theory is used to study the intralaminar damage of CFRP laminates with different stacking sequences under impact loading, and the progressive failure process analysis combining MMF and continuum damage mechanics (CDM) is realized. Bi-linear cohesive model is adopted to capture the initiation and propagation of delamination. Laminates with various stacking sequences including $[90_2, -45_2, 90_2, -45_2]_s$, $[0_2, 45_2, 0_2, 45_2]_s$, $[90_2, 0_2, 90_2, 0_2]_s$, $[0_2, 90_2, 0_2, 90_2]_s$ under low-velocity impact loading are studied. The characteristics of structure response, intralaminar damage and delamination of the four specimens are studied by both simulation and experiments. The effectiveness and validation of the proposed approach are confirmed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to the advantages of light weight, high strength and corrosion resistance, carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite are widely employed in aircraft, automobile and wind blade structure. However, the vulnerability of CFRP to impact loading threatens the structure safety and poses a challenge to the composite material designers. For the reason that the damage mechanism of composite is complicated, superfluous safety factor is often adopted in the structure design process to guarantee the security [1], which causes the increment of mass as well as the energy cost. Therefore, the study on the damage mechanism of impacted composite is of great importance to realize the optimization of composite design [2].

The failure mechanism of CFRP composite can be classified into fiber breakage, matrix crack, interface debonding and delamination [3]. During low-velocity impact condition the perforation

phenomenon is rare, yet the damage area spreads over a large area, among which the delamination is supposed to be the major reason causes the decrease of compressive capacity.

Hong [4] investigated the effects of fiber orientation, thickness, and lamination on the delamination resistance, whose research found a linear relationship between delamination area and impact energy. The study of Hitchen [5] found the energy absorbed in delamination propagation increases linearly with increasing total delamination area, in addition, the compression-after-impact strength is related to the maximum delamination area. Czarnocki [6] found that the amount of dissipated energy substantially varies depending on the reinforcement sequence.

In the simulation of impacted composite the failure theories based on macro-mechanics are commonly adopted. Long [7] investigated the composite laminates subjected to low-velocity impact by Hashin damage criteria. Feng [8] studied the intralaminar failure by the Shurmann and Puck criterion. The damage model of González [9] is based on the LaRC failure criteria, which accounts for the in situ effect of the thickness of a ply on its transverse tensile and shear strengths. The previous failure models are all based on macro-mechanics which treat the composite as homogeneous materials, despite succinct the different stress distribution in the fiber and matrix are neglected.

In this paper, the micro-mechanics of failure (MMF) theory is adopted to capture the intralaminar failure mechanism, and the bi-linear cohesive model is employed to capture the initiation and propagation of delamination. The impact damage of composite laminates with four different stacking sequences is studied by finite element method. The impact loading tests were carried out and the structure response was recorded, after that the damage of the tested specimens was examined by both the visual inspection and the ultrasonic C-scanning. The simulation and experiment results are compared and several conclusions were drawn.

2. INTRALAMINAR DAMAGE MODEL

2.1 THE CALCULATION OF MICRO STRESS

The MMF theory was firstly proposed by Ha [10], which uses the amplification factors to calculate the micro stress of a material point in the composite, along with the constituents failure criteria the initial damage of the material can be captured. As illustrated in Figure 1, the macro stress of a composite structure can be calculated based on classical laminate theory (CLT) or finite element method (FEM), and in order to obtain the micro stress status 17 key points in fiber and 19 key points in matrix are selected respectively, then the following equation is used.

$$\sigma_i = M_\sigma^i \bar{\sigma} + A_\sigma^i \Delta T \quad (1)$$

where σ_i is the micro stress of key point i (The red point in Figure 1), $\bar{\sigma}$ is the macro stress of unit cell, ΔT is the difference between non-stress temperature and ambient temperature, M_σ^i is the mechanical stress amplification factor of point i , A_σ^i is the thermal stress amplification factor of point i , σ_i and $\bar{\sigma}$ are composed of six stress components, M_σ^i is 6×6 matrix, A_σ^i is 6×1 column vector.

Figure 1: Unit cell model and key points location in fiber and matrix.

The calculation procedure of M_{σ}^i and A_{σ}^i can be found in our previous papers [11~12] and will not be repeated here.

2.2 THE INITIAL FAILURE CRITERIA

Noninteractive failure criteria based on the micro stress of a material point are adopted to judge the initial failure of fiber and matrix, which are as follows.

For the key points in fiber:

$$\frac{\sigma_{11}^f}{T_f} = 1 \quad \text{Tensile failure} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\sigma_{eq}^f}{C_f} = 1 \quad \text{Compressive failure} \quad (3)$$

For the key points in matrix:

$$\frac{I_1^m}{T_m} = 1 \quad \text{Tensile failure} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\sigma_{eq}^m}{C_m} = 1 \quad \text{Compressive failure} \quad (5)$$

Where σ_{11}^f and σ_{eq}^f are the longitudinal stress and Mises stress of a key point in the fiber, I_1^m and σ_{eq}^m are the first invariant of stress and Mises stress of a key point in the matrix. The value of T_f , C_f , T_m and C_m are obtained by substituting the unidirectional laminate strength of X , X' , Y and Y' (Table 1) into equation 1. The critical MMF parameters used in this paper are listed in Table 2.

The uniaxial strength of unidirectional laminate		
Longitudinal tensile strength X	[Mpa]	2100
Longitudinal compressive strength X'	[Mpa]	1932
Transverse tensile strength Y	[Mpa]	54
Transverse compressive strength Y'	[Mpa]	179

Table 1: The uniaxial strengths of unidirectional UTS50/E51 laminate

Critical parameters of constituents		
Fiber tensile strength T_f	[Mpa]	3170
Fiber compressive strength C_f	[Mpa]	3400

Matrix tensile strength T_m	[Mpa]	155
Matrix compressive strength C_m	[Mpa]	207

Table 2: MMF parameters of UT50/E51 laminate

2.3 MATERIAL STIFFNESS DEGRADATION

To describe the influence of constituent failure to the load bearing ability, the stiffness degradation strategy proposed by McCarthy [13] is adopted as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 C_{11} &= E_1(1-d_f)[1-(1-d_m)^2\nu_{23}^2]/A \\
 C_{22} &= E_2(1-d_m)[1-(1-d_m)(1-d_f)\nu_{13}\nu_{31}]/A \\
 C_{33} &= E_2(1-d_m)[1-(1-d_m)(1-d_f)\nu_{12}\nu_{21}]/A \\
 C_{12} &= E_2(1-d_m)(1-d_f)[(1-d_m)\nu_{13}\nu_{23} + \nu_{12}]/A \\
 C_{13} &= E_2(1-d_m)(1-d_f)[(1-d_m)\nu_{12}\nu_{23} + \nu_{13}]/A \\
 C_{23} &= E_2(1-d_m)^2[(1-d_f)\nu_{12}\nu_{31} + \nu_{23}]/A \\
 C_{44} &= G_{12}(1-d_m)(1-d_f) \\
 C_{55} &= G_{13}(1-d_m)(1-d_f) \\
 C_{66} &= G_{23}(1-d_m)(1-d_f) \\
 A &= 1-(1-d_m)(1-d_f)\nu_{12}\nu_{21} - (1-d_m)^2\nu_{23}\nu_{32} \\
 &\quad - (1-d_m)(1-d_f)\nu_{13}\nu_{31} - 2(1-d_m)^2(1-d_f)\nu_{12}\nu_{31}\nu_{23}
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where d_f and d_m are the damage indexes of the fiber and matrix in a material point, whose values are initially set as zero. If the micro stress of one key point in the fiber satisfies equation 2 or 3, the value of d_f will be set as 0.99. If the micro stress of one key point in the matrix satisfies equation 4 or 5, the value of d_f will be set as 0.5.

3. INTERLAMINAR DAMAGE MODEL

Bi-linear cohesive model was adopted in this paper to study the initiation and propagation of delamination. The traction-separation relationship is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Traction-separation constitutive relationship of cohesive model.

The stress status of composite under low velocity impact is complex and the delamination often occurs in mixed mode. A quadratic nominal stress criterion was adopted to judge the initiation of delamination:

$$\left(\frac{\langle \sigma_n \rangle}{N} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_s}{S} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_t}{T} \right)^2 = 1 \tag{7}$$

where $\langle \rangle$ represents Macaulay bracket and signifies that a pure compressive deformation or stress state does not initiate delamination.

The criteria used to predict delamination propagation under mixed-mode loading conditions are usually established in terms of the energy release rate and fracture toughness. The mixed-mode criterion proposed by Benzeggagh and Kenane[14] (B–K criterion) is able to account for the variation of fracture toughness as a function of mode ratio in epoxy composites and is adopted in this paper, whose expression is as follows:

$$G_{IC} + (G_{IIC} - G_{IC}) \left(\frac{G_{shear}}{G_T} \right)^\eta = G_{TC} \quad (8)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} G_{shear} &= G_{II} + G_{III} \\ G_T &= G_I + G_{II} + G_{III} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The parameter η can be obtained from MMB tests at different mode ratios, and in this paper it is set as 1.6. The cohesive parameters used in this paper are listed in Table3.

Cohesive properties		Value
K_n	[GPa m ⁻¹]	3.2×10^4
K_t	[GPa m ⁻¹]	3.5×10^4
K_s	[GPa m ⁻¹]	3.5×10^4
N	[MPa]	10
T	[MPa]	15
S	[MPa]	15
G_{IC}	[J m ⁻²]	190
G_{IIC}	[J m ⁻²]	635
G_{IIIC}	[J m ⁻²]	635

Table 3: Cohesive parameters

4. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL AND EXPERIMENT

Finite element model of impacted composite laminate was built on the ABAQUS/Explicit platform. The dimension of the laminate is $150 \times 100 \times 1.6 \text{ mm}^3$, and the single layer is 0.1mm thick as shown in Figure 4a. Four different stacking sequences of $[90_2, -45_2, 90_2, -45_2]_s$, $[0_2, 45_2, 0_2, 45_2]_s$, $[90_2, 0_2, 90_2, 0_2]_s$, $[0_2, 90_2, 0_2, 90_2]_s$ were set. The element type of each layer was C3D8R. The MMF theory and progressive damage were realized by user material subroutine VUMAT. Thin cohesive elements were embedded between layers with different fiber orientation as listed in Table 4, whose thickness is set as 10^{-4} m and the element type is COH3D8. UTS50/E51 prepreg was hot pressed to make the composite laminates with the stacking sequences of $[90_2, -45_2, 90_2, -45_2]_s$ and $[90_2, 0_2, 90_2, 0_2]_s$ as illustrated in Figure 3, then the laminates were cut into specimens as the cut sketch shows.

Layer	Specimen			
	1#	2#	3#	4#
16	90°	0°	90°	0°
15	90°	0°	90°	0°
	coh6	coh6	coh6	coh6
14	-45°	45°	0°	90°
13	-45°	45°	0°	90°
	coh5	coh5	coh5	coh5
12	90°	0°	90°	0°
11	90°	0°	90°	0°
	coh4	coh4	coh4	coh4
10	-45°	45°	0°	90°
9	-45°	45°	0°	90°
8	-45°	45°	0°	90°
7	-45°	45°	0°	90°
	coh3	coh3	coh3	coh3
6	90°	0°	90°	0°
5	90°	0°	90°	0°
	coh2	coh2	coh2	coh2
4	-45°	45°	0°	90°
3	-45°	45°	0°	90°
	coh1	coh1	coh1	coh1
2	90°	0°	90°	0°
1	90°	0°	90°	0°

Impact direction ↓

Figure 3: Cut sketch of specimens

Table 4: Stacking sequences and interlayers of specimens

The mass of impactor is 2.5 Kg and the impact energy is 5.6J. The mechanical and thermal properties used in the FE model are listed in Table 5.

Materials properties	Ply	Fiber	Matrix
Fiber volume fraction V_f	0.56	1.0	0.0
Longitudinal modulus E_1 [GPa]	136	240	3
Transverse modulus $E_2=E_3$ [GPa]	10	42	3
Shear modulus $G_{12}=G_{13}$ [GPa]	4.7	23	1.06
Shear modulus G_{23} [GPa]	3.2	12	1.09
Poisson's ration $\mu_{12}=\mu_{13}$	0.35	0.33	0.38
Poisson's ration μ_{23}	0.56	0.71	0.38
Longitudinal coefficient of thermal expansion α_1 [$10^{-6}K^{-1}$]	-0.34	-0.87	60
Transverse coefficient of thermal expansion $\alpha_2=\alpha_3$ [$10^{-6}K^{-1}$]	75	40	60

Table 5: Mechanical and thermal properties used in the FE model.

The impact experiments were carried out on INSTRON 9350HV test machine (Figure 4b). During the experiments the contact force, displacement and velocity of impactor were recorded. After the experiments the specimens were visually examined and inspected by VEO1664 ultrasonic C-scan equipment, by which the delamination images were acquired.

Figure 4: Finite element model(a) and INSTRON 9350HV low-velocity test machine (b)

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 STRUCTURE RESPONSE

Figure 5 shows the simulation and experiment results of historical contact force. From both Figure 5a and Figure 5b, it can be found that specimen 1 and 2 have equal maximum contact forces, and the time cost before contact force reaches its peak point of specimen 1 is less than specimen 2. Similarly, the maximum contact force of specimen 3 and 4 are the same, and the time cost of specimen 3 is less. In addition, from the experiment results shown in Figure 5b, a difference of about 250 N exists between the maximum contact force of specimen 1 and 3, yet from the simulation results shown in Figure 5a these differences have not presented.

Figure 5: Contact force of specimen with four different stacking sequences.

Figure 6 shows the historical displacement of impactor obtained from simulation and experiments. From both Figure 6a and Figure 6b, it can be found that the impactor displacements of four specimens are the same at the beginning and separate before reaching their peak points, after which they keep detached until returning to zero. The maximum displacement of specimen 1 is less than specimen 2, similarly, specimen 3 less than specimen 4.

The errors of contact force, impactor displacement and their time cost between simulations and experiments are shown in Figure 7a. It can be found that the contact force errors of four specimens are all less than 10%. The overall errors of specimen 2 are the smallest, among which the error of maximum contact force is 4.5%.

Figure 6: Displacement of impactor with four different stacking sequences.

Figure 7: The errors of structure response and delamination between simulations and experiments.

5.2 INTRALAMINAR DAMAGE

For the reason that the impact energy in this paper is as low as 5.6 J, fiber breakage was not found in the laminate both in the simulation and visual inspection. The matrix failure in each layers of four specimens were shown in Figure 8. The shapes of tensile failures of matrix in different specimens are shown in Figure 8a, and the tensile failure areas in each layer are illustrated in Figure 9, in which the tensile failure area decrease from bottom to top layer. The compressive failures of each layer (Figure 8b) in four specimens mainly located in the several top layers and their areas are less than 20 mm^2 , which are much less than tensile failure area.

(a) Tensile failure of matrix (b) Compressive failure of matrix

Figure 8: The matrix failure of four specimens by simulation

Figure 9: Tensile failure area of matrix in each layer of four specimens

5.3 DELAMINATION

The delaminations of four specimens are shown in Figure 10. It can be seen that the propagation direction of delamination changes with the fiber orientation of lower layer adjacent to the interlayer. Taking specimen 1 for example, the delamination depicted by coh1 has the propagation direction coincident with the fiber orientation of lower layer which is 90°, and the same tendency is found in other specimens. The delamination shape in each interlayer of specimen 1 and 2 are the same, the differences of which are their directions and areas, similar phenomenon can be found in specimen 3 and 4. The width and length errors between simulations and experiments are shown in Figure 7b, in which specimen 2 presents the best precision.

(a) Specimen 1

(b) Specimen 2

(c) Specimen 3

(d) Specimen 4

Figure 10. Delamination of four specimens with different stacking sequences

6. CONCLUSIONS

The micro-mechanics of failure (MMF) theory is adopted in this paper to study the intralaminar damage of composite laminate with different stacking sequences. Thin cohesive elements are embedded between layers with different fiber orientations to investigate the initiation and propagation of delamination. Distinct stiffness degradation strategies are used to consider the failure of fiber and matrix. To summarize the simulation and experiment results, the following conclusions were drawn.

(1) The proposed model shows good capacity to calculate the maximum contact force. The error between simulation and experiment results of specimen 2 is quite small. The maximum contact force of specimen 1 and 2 are the same, however, the time cost and displacements of impactor are different. Similar phenomenon can be found between specimen 3 and 4.

(2) Only matrix failures were found in all simulation results under low impact loading energy in this paper. The intralaminar damage mechanism is mainly tensile failure of matrix, and the damage areas of which decrease from the bottom layer to the top layer. The compressive failure of matrix is located in several top layers, and the damage areas are far less than the tensile failure.

(3) The propagation direction of delamination coincides with the fiber orientation of lower layer. The delamination shape of specimen 1 and 3 are the same as specimen 2 and 4 respectively, the differences of which are the areas and directions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by National Science Foundation of China and Civil Aviation Administration of China (NO.U1433119).

REFERENCES

- [1] E. Castillo, R. Míguez, A. Ruiz-Terán, et al, Design of a composite beam using the failure probability-safety factor method, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, **62(9)**, 2004, pp.1148-1182 (doi: [10.1002/nme.1215](https://doi.org/10.1002/nme.1215)).
- [2] D. Feng, F. Aymerich, Damage prediction in composite sandwich panels subjected to low-velocity impact, *Composites Part A Applied Science & Manufacturing*, **52**, 2013, pp.12-22

- (doi:[10.1016/j.compositesa.2013.04.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2013.04.010)).
- [3] L. Maio, E. Monaco, F. Ricci, et al, Simulation of low velocity impact on composite laminates with progressive failure analysis, *Composite Structures*, **103**, 2013, pp.75–85 (doi:[10.1016/j.compstruct.2013.02.027](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2013.02.027)).
- [4] S. Hong, D. Liu, On the relationship between impact energy and delamination area, *Experimental Mechanics*, **29(2)**, 1989, pp.115-120 (doi:[10.1007/BF02321362](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02321362)).
- [5] S. A. Hitchen, R. M. J. Kemp, The effect of stacking sequence on impact damage in a carbon fibre/epoxy composite, *Composites*, **26(3)**, 1995, pp.207-214. (doi:[10.1016/0010-4361\(95\)91384-H](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-4361(95)91384-H))
- [6] P. Czanocki, Delamination resistance of laminates with various stacking sequences against low velocity impacts, *Solid State Phenomena*, **240**, 2015, pp.143-148 (doi:[10.4028/www.scientific.net/SSP.240.143](https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/SSP.240.143)) .
- [7] S. Long, X. Yao, X. Zhang, Delamination prediction in composite laminates under low-velocity impact, *Composite Structures*, **132**, 2015, pp.290-298 (doi:[10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.05.037](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.05.037)).
- [8] D. Feng, F. Aymerich, Finite element modelling of damage induced by low-velocity impact on composite laminates, *Composite Structures*, **108(1)**, 2014, pp.161–171 (doi:[10.1016/j.compstruct.2013.09.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2013.09.004)) .
- [9] E.V. González, P. Maimí, P.P. Camanho, et al, Simulation of drop-weight impact and compression after impact tests on composite laminates, *Composite Structures*, **94(11)**, 2012, pp.3364-3378 (doi:[10.1016/j.compstruct.2012.05.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2012.05.015)) .
- [10] S.K. Ha, K.K. Jin, Y. Huang, Micro-Mechanics of Failure (MMF) for Continuous Fiber Reinforced Composites, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **42(18)**, 2008, pp.1873-1895. (doi:[10.1177/0021998308093911](https://doi.org/10.1177/0021998308093911)).
- [11] W. Li, H. Cai, C. Li, et al, Progressive failure of laminated composites with a hole under compressive loading based on micro-mechanics, *Advanced Composite Materials*, **23**, 2014, pp.477-490 (doi:[10.1080/09243046.2014.915105](https://doi.org/10.1080/09243046.2014.915105)).
- [12] W. Li, H. Cai, C. Li, et al, Micro-mechanics of failure for fatigue strength prediction of bolted joint structures of carbon fiber reinforced polymer composite, *Composite Structures*, **124**, 2015, pp.345-356. (doi:[10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.01.026](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.01.026)).
- [13] C.T. McCarthy, R.M. O'Higgins, R.M. Frizzell, A cubic spline implementation of non-linear shear behaviour in three-dimensional progressive damage models for composite laminates, **92(1)**, *Composite Structures*, 2010, pp.173-181 (doi:[10.1016/j.compstruct.2009.07.025](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2009.07.025)).
- [14] M.L. Benzeggagh, M. Kenane, Measurement of mixed-mode delamination fracture toughness of unidirectional glass/epoxy composites with mixed-mode bending apparatus, *Composites Science & Technology*, **56(4)**, 1996, pp.439-449. (doi:[10.1016/0266-3538\(96\)00005-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0266-3538(96)00005-X)).